

AUTOMATED CABIN AND CARGO LINING AND HAT RACK INSTALLATION FOR THE AIRCRAFT FACTORY OF TOMORROW

L. Brieskorn⁽¹⁾, D. Niermann⁽²⁾, S. Kothe⁽³⁾, M. Wolf⁽⁴⁾, P. Rawal⁽⁵⁾, T. Hass⁽⁶⁾

⁽¹⁾ Fraunhofer IFAM, Ottenbecker Damm 12, 21684 Stade, (Germany), leander.brieskorn@ifam.fraunhofer.de

⁽²⁾ Fraunhofer IFAM, Ottenbecker Damm 12, 21684 Stade, (Germany), dirk.niermann@ifam.fraunhofer.de

⁽³⁾ Fraunhofer IFAM, Wiener Straße 12, 28359 Bremen, (Germany), simon.kothe@ifam.fraunhofer.de

⁽⁴⁾ Fraunhofer IFAM, Wiener Straße 12, 28359 Bremen, (Germany), michael.wolf@ifam.fraunhofer.de

⁽⁵⁾ Fraunhofer IFAM, Ottenbecker Damm 12, 21684 Stade, (Germany), parth.kapil.rawal@ifam.fraunhofer.de

⁽⁶⁾ Fraunhofer IFAM, Ottenbecker Damm 12, 21684 Stade, (Germany), tim.hass@ifam.fraunhofer.de

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ABSTRACT:

Aircraft assembly is currently mainly performed manually resulting in partly non-ergonomic or inefficient processes. Automated assistance systems can overcome these challenges. This paper presents results of the Clean Sky 2, Large Passenger Aircraft (LPA) cluster project ACCLAIM (Automated Cabin and Cargo Lining and Hat Rack Installation Method) managed by the Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM. Improvements of assembly and installation process of cabin and cargo lining and overhead compartment elements are shown. The focus is on the validation of the development results of project partners with the help of a fuselage mock-up built by Fraunhofer IFAM. Based on the accumulated experience, furthermore opportunities of cabin and cargo assembly automation are addressed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Growing demand for aircrafts and the highly competitive global market call for versatile and cost-effective aircraft production systems with high efficiency. To achieve this goal, a high degree of automation is essential. However, aircraft cabin and cargo assembly tasks such as installation of linings and overhead compartments are hard to automate as the geometry of the structures varies significantly. To overcome this challenge with state-of-the-art automation technology is not possible – the conventional teach-in programmed industrial robots will fail due to a limited flexibility and weight restrictions [1]. Therefore, aircraft cabin and cargo assembly tasks are currently mainly performed manually by humans resulting partly in inefficient processes and frequently in ergonomically unfavorable postures [2].

A new approach is the application of sensor-guided, lightweight, mobile, collaborative industrial robots that are on one hand capable of cooperating with humans and on the other hand capable to adapting to the varying geometries of the structures. Based on such systems the different skills of robots and humans can be combined in an effective solution-oriented way. Nevertheless, based on today's design of cabin and cargo interior parts that is substantially optimized for manual assembly, such a combined strategy might fail [3]. This demands a part design, which meets automation requirements.

Figure 1. Vision of future cabin and cargo assembly

Figure 1 visualizes the initial idea of the project ACCLAIM – a sub-project of Large Passenger Aircraft (LPA), Next Generation Cabin and Cargo, within the framework of the European research program Clean Sky 2 funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 program. The overall objective was to develop automation strategies for cabin and cargo assembly for commercial aircrafts.

ACCLAIM is a cluster of four partner projects. SIMFAL (assembly planning by simulation) was carried out by Asociación Centro Tecnológico Ceit-ik4 and CT Ingenieros Aeronauticos de Automocione Industriales SL; CALITO (design and manufacture of sidewall panels and hat racks) by SFS intec GmbH and Solvay Speciality Polymers Belgium SA/NV; EURECA (human-robot cooperation for cabin and cargo assembly tasks) by Istituto di Tecnologie Industriali e Automazione -

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, IT+ Robotics SRL, Protom Group S.p.A. and University of Padova; and VISTA (inspection after the installation phase) by Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Lin Up SRL and PROTOM Group S.p.A.. Fraunhofer IFAM took over the topic management and Airbus S.A.S. provided use-cases and requirements for all projects.

Besides managing the project consortia, Fraunhofer IFAM constructed a validation platform representing the critical assembly requirements and restrictions of an A320 fuselage in the Final Assembly Line.

This work was focused on the concept and design of the fuselage mock-up as well as on the program to validate the ACCLAIM results both on single project level and by combining all technologies to form a coherent system. Experiences from the validation process were analyzed and limits and opportunities of collaborative cabin and cargo assembly automation were derived from it.

2. THE FUSELAGE MOCK-UP

The fuselage mock-up was constructed to validate strategies for automated cabin and cargo installation within the project ACCLAIM. It allows to perform and analyze either collaborative (human-robot) or solely manual or mixed assembly strategies.

Figure 2. Concept of the fuselage mock-up

Figure 2 shows a rendering of the fuselage mock-up, representing a section of an A320 single aisle aircraft. As illustrated, it includes a cabin and a cargo area, assembly platforms on each level to bring equipment inside the fuselage as well as an elevator to raise the equipment from the base area to the particular level where it is needed.

Figure 3. Open section of the fuselage mock-up

In contrast to the real setup in the Final Assembly Line the cross sections of the fuselage remain open and accessible from the outside for the ease of transportation of equipment as well as a better observation of processes (see Figure 3). The mock-up was designed to provide a realistic assembly environment for the following tasks:

- 1) Automated localization of connecting brackets and referencing to their positions
- 2) Automated installation of parts with a suitable design such as cabin sidewall panels, cargo sidewall panels, ceiling panels, overhead compartments or brackets designed for automation
- 3) Installation assistance of humans by robotic systems as well as by virtual reality and augmented reality tools
- 4) Logistic processes including autonomous transport of tools, systems, parts and auxiliary equipment
- 5) Verification of the correct assembly, final positions and alignment of these parts by automated testing

The usability of the mock-up is not just limited to the listed tasks. After all, the cabin and cargo area assembly includes many further operations. The project, however, had to focus on a few typical and representative applications to demonstrate the general feasibility of robotic processes with such severe restrictions. These relate primarily to space inside the cabin, to floor loadings, to payloads of the robots, to power and data supply, to accessibility from the outside, to the elevation above ground level, to lighting conditions, to vibrations and structural deformations and, last but not least, to safety aspects of human-robot co-existence and co-operation.

Within ACCLAIM, the sub-project CALITO developed and provided linings and hat racks including brackets for automated installation. The sub-project EURECA focused on mobile systems for automated assembly. One important constraint for the development of the robotic systems was the maximum permissible floor load of an AIRBUS A320, which required lightweight automation systems based on appropriate mobile platforms (AGVs) and robots. SIMFAL made their processes and tools in assembly simulation, planning and assistance with a simulation environment based on VR and AR available. Finally, solutions for automated quality insurance came from the VISTA project.

Figure 4. Development of the fuselage mock-up

Figure 4 shows the construction progress of the validation platform from semi-circle frames to a full fuselage section. The assembly of the initially virtually designed (CAD) mock-up was supported by contactless metrology systems, e.g. laser tracker and laser radar. Following the design principles of the state-of-the-art A320 fuselage, the mock-up was constructed to the special needs and frame conditions of the project.

To keep expenses as low as possible, a CFRP-fuselage skin was recycled from a former project and combined with aluminum frames and stringers provided by AIRBUS to form a single aisle diameter. Using non-aircraft grade aluminum profiles and sandwich plates for the design and construction of the passenger and cargo floors and the support structures led to further cost reductions.

Additional advantages of this approach were some design modifications, which allow a broader range of solutions to be tested and validated. For example, the floor structure was reinforced to support also the test of heavier equipment and the cargo area was equipped with mounting plates to ease the quick exchange of different bracket systems in the development and validation phase.

A plus point of the need to cut the openings of windows, passenger and cargo doors out of the fuselage skin was an opportunity to test the flexibility and accuracy of a mobile sensor-guided robotic machining system with this task (see figure 5).

Figure 5. Cutting the windows of the fuselage mock-up

The system, previously developed in the project ProsiHP2 [4] funded by the Lower Saxony Ministry for Economic Affairs, Technology and Transport, passed the test with distinction.

Figure 6. Fuselage mock-up with elevator

Special attention was paid to the integration of an elevator system as shown in Figure 6. Besides safety and robustness, the capability to communicate directly with mobile, autonomous navigating transport systems or robots was of high priority. For this reason Fraunhofer IFAM equipped the elevator with an own PLC-control including an OPC UA [5] interface. This way the elevator became an integrated element of the automation solutions.

3. VALIDATION OF PARTNER'S DEVELOPMENTS

After commissioning, the fuselage mock-up was initially used for the validation of the development results of EURECA (mobile robot systems for automated installation) and CALITO (cabin and cargo lining and hat rack structures), before in a second phase the interaction with SIMFAL (assembly planning by simulation) was demonstrated.

The process chain started with the application of the SIMFAL VR tool, based on a digital twin, to test different assembly variants and select the best alternative according to preset criteria including ergonomics, safety, productivity, or spatial restrictions. The digital twin in a virtual reality also helped to guide and control the robotic systems during the assembly, while augmented reality

systems assisted the worker by visualizing and monitoring actual information in real-time.

After the process planning and simulation tools transmitted suitable data to the AGV-based robot systems provided by EURECA, these moved to the mock-up and requested the elevator. For this purpose, the robots integrated OPC UA client sent the request directly to the SPS-control of the elevator, which responded and lifted the mobile system to the cabin level. In the same manner, the modular robot system transported the linings and overhead compartments provided by CALITO from the storage area on ground level to the cabin.

After all parts and robots arrived inside the cabin or the cargo area, at first they performed the lining installation. Therefore, the transport module with the linings on top approached the working module, which grabbed the uppermost lining with a lightweight vacuum gripper. A camera, attached to the working module, monitored positions and movements, which permanently were synchronized and adjusted by the SIMFAL VR tool (figure 7)

Figure 7. Automated cabin lining installation

Then the camera was used to guide the lightweight robot to the correct installation position in front of the cabin wall and the system inserted the lining accurately into a rail on floor level. In a next step the robot arm tilted the part against the cabin wall until the window openings of the lining clipped into the window frames. Finally, a human worker closed a clamping cover on top of the lining. This last step could have been easily be automated too, but it was carried out in a human robot co-operative way because an immediate visual and manual inspection by a worker was considered to be appropriate.

The limited height of the cargo area required a reconfiguration of the modular robot working module, as shown in figure 8. Due to the different geometries of the linings and the structure they had to be attached to, CALITO developed a further

tailor-made fastening system. It bases on conical fastening clips, which allow load transmission in all directions, tolerance compensation in two directions and an easy installation inspection.

Figure 8. Automated cargo lining installation

For the installation of overhead compartments originally a human robot co-operation was planned with the robot taking over the function of a lifting aid and the worker to guide the heavy part in position and to fix it. However, during the development phase it was found that the robotic system is also capable to carry out the positioning and the fixing, so that the human could be exempted from this task.

Figure 9. Automated overhead compartment installation

This is made possible by the positioning and the referencing capabilities of the robot and by the automation supporting fastening system from the CALITO project. It includes hooks as upper attachments, which allow a downward rotation of the hooked-in box to fasten a lower attachment.

The validation results proved that the VR/AR-Tools of SIMFAL, the robots of EURECA, and the cabin and cargo parts of CALITO, which all were specifically designed to meet the requirements of automated assembly, together form a very efficient system with high potential for future use in aircraft production.

The virtual simulation and planning environment provided by SIMFAL supported a detailed step-by-step-optimization of the assembly systems and structures before real-life-implementation.

CALITO provided structures with a bracket-less design, offering innovative self-adjusting interfaces for optimized automated assembly. Due to this, the installation process is up to five times faster than the installation of the conventional manual process. The reason is that no more complex screwing processes are needed to assemble the lining parts, facilitating automation of the assembly processes. All the described fastener systems from CALITO also permit an easy uninstallation.

Being partly made out of foam, the overall weight of the lining parts could be reduced by 24 %. The benefit of this weight reduction is not only less fuel consumption of the aircraft due to less weight. The weight reduction is also helpful for the design of the assembly systems since less weight has to be moved during the assembly process. Fortunately, the foam design of the parts did not only allow lightweight but also low-cost structures, resulting in cost savings of up to 15 %.

Figure 10. Final installed cabin parts

In near future the ACCLAIM validation will be completed by VISTA with a demonstration of the robot-based visual inspection.

4. CONCLUSION

The CS2-ACCLAIM fuselage mock-up of Fraunhofer IFAM has proved its suitability for the validation of the automated, VR/AR-controlled installation of cabin and cargo linings and overhead compartments.

The demonstrated processes showed that modular, AGV based solutions provide a high degree of versatility and help to avoid ergonomically unfavorable work. By the integration of safety sensors, scanners or cameras a complete autonomous process is achievable.

The EURECA project demonstrated that mobile robotic systems are capable of installing the components properly and autonomously. Even heavier parts like overhead compartments could be lifted, mounted and installed. However, a difference in operational speed between human workforce and significantly slower automated systems remains.

Overall, the primary benefit of automated cabin part installation is the avoidance of non-ergonomic body postures, as the complete assembly will be done partly or completely by the robots. A digital twin, provided by SIMFAL, allows monitoring of the automated process safely from a remote workstation. Moreover, easy installation and uninstallation due to the highly functional part design from the CALITO project holds the potential to become more time and cost efficient in future if further development accelerates the automated processes. Perspectively, cost reduction and the better working conditions will lead to a greater acceptance of automation in aircraft production allowing a step forward in cabin and cargo assembly of a single aisle aircraft.

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